

Prediction and Validation of Crush Behaviors in Advanced Glass Mat Thermoplastic Tubes Using Innovative Simulation Technology

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Introduction

Motivation & Background

☑ What is GMT (Glass Mat Thermoplastics)?

- lightweight composite material that uses thermoplastic resin as a matrix and glass fiber mat as a reinforced skeleton

☑ Key Advantages

- High specific strength, Excellent impact resistance
- Good formability for complex shapes
- Recyclability suitable for sustainable applications.

Glass Mat Thermoplastic(GMT) Composites for Automotive Applications

*Source: <https://ilucku.com/>

☐ Glass Mat Thermoplastic Sheets

*Source: <https://www.fiberglassfiber.com/>

☐ Application to automotive parts

- Bumper System
- Battery enclosures
- Under body
- Crash boxes
- Seat frames
- Dashboard
- Others

Motivation & Background

☑ Failure mode & Crashworthiness of GMT tubes

- Stable progressive splaying failure mode enabled by high toughness of thermoplastic matrix.
- Enhanced crash energy absorption significantly

☑ Modeling & Simulation Requirements

- Material modeling for progressive failure in GMT tube with random fiber orientation
- Efficient FE modeling to replicate both the splaying failure and energy absorption response

☑ Aim of this study

- Analysis of failure and energy absorption behavior of Advanced GMT Tubes
- Proposal of a practical crash simulation framework for GMT tubes

	Thermoset composites tube	Thermoplastic composites tube(GMT)
Comparison of Failure modes	<p style="text-align: center;"> • <u>Lamina bending & Splaying Failure Mode</u> </p>	

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02

Material Characterization

Advanced Glass Mat Thermoplastic

Multi-layered Hybrid(MLH) Mat

- Fabricated by alternately stacking resin films and chopped long glass fibers
- Minimized the resin flow path improving the impregnation quality of high-viscosity thermoplastic resin

Fabrication of MLH-mat composites

- GF/PA6 MLH-mat ▶ Glass fiber mat – 125 g/m², PA6 resin films – 33 g/m²
- 26 plies stacked to form MLH-mat composite plates ▶ Total thickness : 2.4 mm , Fiber volume : 40 % vol.

Multi-layered Hybrid(MLH) mat – Advanced Glass Mat Thermoplastic

Mechanical properties and Fracture toughness evaluation

☑ Static mechanical properties

- Tensile, Compressive and In-plane shear Tests results

Static mechanical properties

Tension – ASTM D3039

Compression – ASTM D3410

Property	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Poisson's Ratio
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Tension in longitudinal dir.	250	13.1	0.32
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Tension in transverse dir.	260	12.5	0.32
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Compression in longitudinal dir.	174	15.1	-
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Compression in transverse dir.	162	14.9	-
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In-plane shear	132	5.0	-
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Mechanical properties and Fracture toughness evaluation

Fracture toughness evaluation

- Inter-laminar fracture toughness : ① Mode I (DCB tests) = 2.74 kJ/m² | ② Mode II (ELS tests) = 2.34 kJ/m²
- Intra-laminar fracture toughness : ① Compact Tension = 37.4 kJ/m² | ② Compact Compression = 40.2 kJ/m²

Inter-laminar fracture toughness tests

Mode I (Double Cantilever Beam) tests results

Mode II (End-Loaded Split) tests results

Intra-laminar fracture toughness tests

Compact tension

Compact compression

chapter

03

Material Modeling

3D Progressive damage model for MLH-mat composites

☑ Motivation for material modeling of MLH-mat composites

- Requirement for a material model **suited for randomly oriented fiber-reinforced composites**
- Need for a damage mechanics-based model incorporating experimentally measured fracture toughness

☑ Modeling Strategy – Damage initiation

- Modification of **the 3D Hashin-type failure criterion** for randomly oriented fiber-reinforced composites
- Inclusion of shear stress effects in all directions to reflect matrix-dominated failure

Material modeling for MLH-mat composites

☐ Schematic diagram of randomly oriented fiber composites

Failure mode	Damage initiation criteria
$\sigma_{11} \geq 0$	$f_{1T} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{1T}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
$\sigma_{11} < 0$	$f_{1C} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{1C}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
$\sigma_{22} \geq 0$	$f_{2T} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{2T}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
$\sigma_{22} < 0$	$f_{2C} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{2C}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
$\sigma_{33} \geq 0$	$f_{3T} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{3T}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
$\sigma_{33} < 0$	$f_{3C} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{3C}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$
Shear failure in 1-2 plane	$f_{12} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2$
Shear failure in 2-3 plane	$f_{23} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2$
Shear failure in 1-3 plane	$f_{13} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$

☐ Modification of the 3D Hashin-type damage initiation criterion

3D Progressive damage model for MLH-mat composites

☑ Modeling Strategy – Damage evolution

- Adoption of a **constitutive model** based on the **Continuum Damage Mechanics(CDM)**
- Simulation of **gradual stiffness degradation** during progressive damage evolution
- Incorporation of **intra-laminar fracture toughness** for realistic simulation of **complex damage mechanisms** in composite structures
- Implementation of the 3D progressive damage model into **LS-DYNA solver** using **UMAT subroutine**

Material modeling for MLH-mat composites

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{S} : \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{S} : \mathbf{M} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{H}\boldsymbol{\sigma} \Rightarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{C}_d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$$

$$\mathbf{C}_d = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & C_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow$$

Symmetric

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= (1-d_1)E_1[1-(1-d_2)(1-d_3)v_{32}v_{23}]/\Delta \\ C_{22} &= (1-d_2)E_2[1-(1-d_1)(1-d_3)v_{13}v_{31}]/\Delta \\ C_{33} &= (1-d_3)E_3[1-(1-d_1)(1-d_2)v_{12}v_{21}]/\Delta \\ C_{12} &= (1-d_1)(1-d_2)E_1[v_{21}+(1-d_3)v_{31}v_{23}]/\Delta \\ C_{13} &= (1-d_1)(1-d_3)E_1[v_{31}+(1-d_2)v_{21}v_{32}]/\Delta \\ C_{23} &= (1-d_2)(1-d_3)E_2[v_{32}+(1-d_1)v_{12}v_{31}]/\Delta \\ C_{44} &= (1-d_{12})G_{12} \\ C_{55} &= (1-d_{23})G_{23} \\ C_{66} &= (1-d_{13})G_{13} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta = 1 - (1-d_2)(1-d_3)v_{32}v_{23} - (1-d_1)(1-d_3)v_{31}v_{13} - (1-d_1)(1-d_2)v_{21}v_{12} - 2(1-d_1)(1-d_2)(1-d_3)v_{13}v_{21}v_{32}$$

☐ progressive constitutive model based on continuum damage mechanics

chapter

04

Crush Test & Simulation

Crush tests of the MLH-mat Tubes

☑ Specimen preparation

- **Shape** : A circular cylindrical shell with flat vertical flanges on both sides
- **Fabrication process** : Hot forming of two half-shells with flat flanges, followed by thermal fusion bonding along the flanges

☑ Test Conditions & Results

- **Test conditions** : ① Impactor Mass = 90.9 kg | ② Impact velocity = 7.86 m/s
- **Test Results(Ave.)** : ① Specific Energy Absorption(SEA) = 48.9 J/g | ② Crush depth = 57.9 mm

Crush Tests of the MLH-mat Tubes

☐ Specimen dimension

☐ Crush test setup

☐ Crush test results (Final shape | Force-displacement curves)

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

☑ FE model of the MLH-mat tube

- Solid elements with four layers along the thickness direction to enhance computational efficiency
- Cohesive elements embedded at the mid-plane of the MLH-mat tube to enable the splaying failure mode
- Rigid body elements used for the impactor, matching the conditions of the physical crush test

☑ Material model

- MLH-mat material ⇒ Proposed 3D Progressive damage model
- Interlaminar behavior ⇒ Cohesive material model (MAT_COHESIVE_MIXED_MODE in LS-DYNA)

Crush Tests of the MLH-mat Tubes

Stiffness	E_1 [MPa]	E_2 [MPa]	E_3 [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	G_{23} [MPa]	G_{13} [MPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	ν_{13}
	13,100	12460	12460	5032	5032	5032	0.32	0.32	0.32
Strength	$X1T$ [MPa]	$X1C$ [MPa]	$X2T$ [MPa]	$X2C$ [MPa]	$X3T$ [MPa]	$X3C$ [MPa]	S12	S23	S13
	250	174	260	162	260	162	132.8	132.8	132.8
Fracture toughness	G1T [kJ/m ²]	G1C [kJ/m ²]	G2T [kJ/m ²]	G2C [kJ/m ²]	G3T [kJ/m ²]	G3C [kJ/m ²]			
	112.9	37.9	112.9	37.9	112.9	37.9			

Intra-laminar fracture toughness

☐ Material parameters of the proposed 3D progressive damage model

	MID	RO [g/m ³]	ROFLG	INTFAIL	EN	ET	GIC	GIIC
1	3	3.30e-5	1.0	1.0	3,000	3,000	2.88 (To be Calibrated)	2.30 (To be Calibrated)
2	XMU	T	S	UND	UTD	GAMMA		
	1.0	80.0	80.0	0	0	1.0		

Inter-laminar fracture toughness

☐ Material parameters of the cohesive material model

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

☑ Initial simulation result

- Observation of a stable splaying failure mode enabled by cohesive element deletion under impact loading
- Underestimation of energy absorption performance due to simplified modeling of interlaminar fracture
 - FE simulation → Interlaminar fracture only considered at the mid-plane of the tube for computational efficiency
 - Actual test → Interlaminar fracture observed at multiple ply interfaces throughout the thickness
- Necessary to calibrate interlaminar fracture toughness to match the experimental energy absorption performance

Crush Simulation Results before calibration

☐ Sequential images of the MLH-tube in the initial crush simulation

☐ Force-displacement curve of crush simulation before calibration

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

☑ Calibration for interlaminar fracture toughness

- Proposal of a fracture toughness correction factor (λ) to adjust the interlaminar fracture toughness value for crash analysis
- Definition of λ as a multiplier applied to Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness from experimental tests
- Establishment of an objective function based on the difference between force–displacement curves from test and simulation
- Optimization of λ using LS-OPT with the response surface method, finally converged to 6.87

Crush Simulation Results before calibration

☐ Fracture toughness correction factor(λ)

$$G_{IC}^{FEA} = \lambda \cdot G_{IC}^{Exp}$$

$$G_{IIC}^{FEA} = \lambda \cdot G_{IIC}^{Exp}$$

☐ Definition of object function

Find λ

To minimize

$$f(\lambda) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \int_{i=0}^n (y(x_i) - \hat{y}_\lambda(x_i))^2}$$

Subjected to $1 \leq \lambda \leq 10$

$y(x_i)$: Force from simulation

$\hat{y}_\lambda(x_i)$: Force from tests

☐ Optimization of calibration parameter for interlaminar fracture toughness using LS-OPT

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

☑ Simulation results after calibration

- Visualization of stable crushing and complete energy absorption in the optimized crush analysis
- Increase in mean crash force and energy absorption, reaching values comparable with experimental results
⇒ Prediction Results : ① SEA = 48.4 J/g | ② Crush depth = 60.3 mm
- Excellent agreement with experimental results, with small deviation of 1.02% for SEA, and 4.14% for crush depth
- Confirmation of λ as a critical factor in improving prediction accuracy of crash energy absorption for the MLH-mat tube

Crush Simulation Results after calibration

☐ Sequential images of the MLH-tube in crush simulation after calibration

☐ Force-displacement curves of crush simulation after calibration

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

☑ Failure mechanism and energy absorption

- Identification of the **splaying failure mechanism** through optimized crush simulation and comparison with test results
- Observation of **Mode I delamination** as the **dominant cause of splaying**, triggered by **debris wedge formation** at the crash front
- **Quantitative analysis** showing **interlaminar failure contributes to 39.4%** and **intralaminar failure to 61.6%** of total absorbed energy
- **Emphasis on** the critical role for **accurate estimation of energy absorption by interlaminar failure**

Crush Simulation of MLH-mat Tubes

Validation under geometry variation

- Necessary to validate applicability of the proposed crush simulation method under tube geometry variation
- Application of the same correction factor ($\lambda = 6.87$) to tubes with 2.3 mm and 3.1 mm thickness
- Consistent crush simulation results with test results within deviation of 5.1% for SEA and crush depth
- Demonstration of reliability and applicability for the proposed method under moderate geometric changes without re-calibration

Validation of the proposed method for dimensional variation

Crush test and simulation results (Thickness = 2.3 mm)

Crush test and simulation results (Thickness = 3.1 mm)

chapter

04

Conclusion

Conclusions

- ☑ **Characterized** the mechanical properties and fracture toughness of **the MLH-mat material**, confirming its quasi-isotropic behavior due to **random fiber orientation**
- ☑ **Developed** a crash analysis method using a **3D progressive damage model** and **mid-plane cohesive elements** to **simulate splaying failure**
- ☑ **Introduced** a **fracture toughness correction factor (λ)** and optimized it to ensure **accurate prediction of energy absorption**
- ☑ **Proposed** a **practical crush analysis framework** for industrial application, demonstrating **reliable performance** under **moderate geometric variation**.

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your kind attention

